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B74. Chitin and Chitosan in Adhesives for Wood-Based Panel Production

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The growing concern over environmental pollution and its consequences on health has encouraged the wood industry to develop environmentally friendly wood adhesives. Even though the market share of bio-based wood adhesives is still small, it has been shown that they can compete with petroleum-based adhesives and be considered an interesting alternative to traditional petroleum-based products. Bio-based adhesives have several advantages over adhesives derived from fossil resources, including biodegradability, lower toxicity, lower carbon footprint, positive impact on climate change, and sustainable design [1]. One of the highest abundant biopolymers on earth after cellulose, which has received wide attention for several commercial applications, is chitin [2,3].

The CHIMAR research team in the EU project Valuable (VALorisation of fUngAl Biomass using novel Enzymatic technology) framework developed adhesives modified with chitosan, which had been derived from crustaceans and *Aspergillus niger* biomass waste. The resin properties were determined using standard lab analysis techniques, and their bonding ability was tested in particleboard and plywood-type panel production at the lab scale, following a simulation of the industrial practice. The produced panels were evaluated according to the prevailing European standards. Moreover, since chitosan, due to its free amine (NH₂) groups, has the potential to adsorb free and hydrolyzed formaldehyde from wood-based panels, its application as an environmentally friendly formaldehyde scavenger in wood-based panels was assessed as well.

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